

THE PROBLEMS OF FARMERS AND TRADERS OF COCONUT BY-PRODUCTS: A CASE STUDY OF COIMATORE DISTRICT OF TAMILNADU

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Abstract

Agriculture is the main occupation of many in Palakkad district, It has given an opportunity for the agriculturists to lead their life in a self-contempt way. The present study analyzed the problems of farmers and traders of coconut by-products in Coimbatore district of Tamilnadu. The study applying the random sampling technique for coconut product manufacturers and marketers were employed to analyze and interpret the data. Simple frequency, Factor Analysis, Anova and Chi-square test. Over the years the producers have faced different environments which made them survived in high latitudes, drought, soil, resistance and so on, of all these problems, the coconut industry has grown significantly by producing, marketing with the available infrastructure facilities. The farmers have to diverse their farming practices. This will give the additional revenue and ways for sustaining profit. The researchers, scientists, farmers have to be in a forum to exchange ideas and transmit the ideas in to action for enhancing sustainability. Coconut marketing will bring addition revenue, if the market segmentations are properly made by concentrating the expectation of different customers groups. As the products of coconuts are lined up, different marketing strategies have to be adopted for better sales. The aspects of branding, customised marketing and reorienting towards value addition will fetch better results.

Key words : coconut, Agriculture, Farmers, Product

Introduction

The coconut palm is botanically referred to as the 'Coco's nucifera'. It is a member of the caeca or palm family. In fact, the coconut palm is the only member of the genus *Coco's*. The palm thrives in the tropical regions and is a major trade component due to its various decorative, culinary and other non-culinary uses. The coconut fruit and palm are believed to have their roots on South Asian soil. Research reveals that the palm is native to the Ganges Delta, in Asia. There are a number of studies that also claim that the fruit has its origin in the northwestern region of South America. There are a number of fossil records that are being researched upon. Some of the fossils found in New Zealand are indicative of the fact that the palm thrived along the New Zealand coast as far back as 15 million years ago.

Primarily, early stage coconuts are harvested from coconut trees for the purpose of coconut water. It is called Tender coconut. The dried coconuts are harvested and stored until the fibrous husks are completely dry. The following main products are produced from the coconut trees. Tender Coconut Water, Copra, Coconut Oil, Raw Kernel, Coconut, Cake, Coconut Toddy, Coconut Shell based Products, Coconut Wood based Products, Coconut Leaves and Coir Pith.

Other than these, Coconut Product are manufactured from the coconut like, Activated carbon, Ball copra, Coconut, Coconut biscuit, Coconut chips, Coconut chutney powder, Coconut honey, Coconut husk, Coconut husk handicrafts, Coconut jaggery, Coconut jam, Coconut milk and cream, Coconut milk powder spraydried, Coconut oil, Coconut oil - Medicated, Coconut shell handicrafts, Coconut shell ice cream cups, Coconut shell powder, Coconut squash, Coconut sweets, Coconut vinegar, Coconut water concentrate, Coconut water soda, Coconut wood handicrafts, Coir pith briquet, Coir products, Copra, Desiccated coconut, Nata de cocoa, Technology Source, Tender coconut, Tender coconut Minimal processed, Tender coconut snowball, Tender coconut water – packed, Theyal mix. These products manufacturers are availed required support from the local area. Even though, they are facing many problems in production and marketing.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

It was observed that the studies under review were based on large samples at the macro level with a limited scope of enquiry, and had certain major deficiencies. During the evaluation, it was found that these studies did not go into the aspects of performance of the coconut products

marketing, a few traders (Sellers) on actual problems faced by coconut products marketing and inland marketers and exporters. Hence the purpose of the present work is assessing the problems in coconut products marketing. The researcher has conducted interviews with few coconut products manufactures in Palakkad district. They expressed many problems in term of finance, labour, raw material non-availability, insufficient technology and training, poor marketing etc. So, it was concluded that required study to give solution for their problems.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The objectives of the study are given below.

- To analyse the demographic, business related information of marketers and producers.
- To analyse the various problems faced by the producers while marketing the coconut products.
- To evaluate the problems faced by the manufacturer while producing coconut products.
- To assess the relationship between the demographic, business information with respect to production and marketing.

1.5. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

The coconut products sellers are facing innumerable problems and some observed by the researcher as follows:

- Huge maintenance expenses are incurred by the sellers.
- The coconut products sellers are facing problems in getting good quality of coconut products in cheaper cost in throughout the year.
- Central and state governments are not providing necessary assistance to all coconut products manufacturers and sellers.
- Frequently coconut products prices are fluctuating without any reasons.
- Perishable and unsold coconut products are not taken by distributor/ manufacturers.

These problems need to be identified and addressed for suitable solution.

1. 6. LIMITATION OF THE STUDY:

A study, which is based on the information form records, documents, research files, is further subject to limitation of the record information. Though an attempt has been made to the

growth of coconut Products production, customers, consumers, salesmen, suppliers, trader/shopkeepers and government officials' problems, trader/shopkeepers financial problems and its prospects in Palakkad district, in depth, the study suffers from following limitations.

- ❖ The study is based upon the survey of opinion of traders and shopkeepers. By using appropriate sampling technique and hence subject to the limitations of any sample survey.
- ❖ The survey essentially relates to opinion on marketers of coconut products manufactures, and marketing of coconut products.

METHODOLOGY AND TOOLS:

Types of data: This research is based on both primary data secondary data.

Primary data The researcher designed a questionnaire for collecting primary data, with the assistance of selected coconut Products marketers. Questions related to various aspects of source of coconut products, Items of products, nature of the shop, infrastructure facilities, marketing methods, insurance, marketing development assistance, source of export, and other facilities were incorporated in the questionnaire. The data were collected 200 samples for both coconut products manufacturers and coconut product marketers.

Secondary data: The researcher accessed the data available with Coconut products production co-operative centers, offices of the apex bodies of foreign trade in India, such as Export Promotion Councils, a renowned research institute under Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR), Ministry of Agriculture, Government of India, and Coconut Development Board.

Sampling Scheme. The survey was conducted by applying the random sampling technique for coconut product manufacturers and marketers.

TOOLS OF ANALYSIS:

The following statistical tools were employed to analyze and interpret the data. Simple frequency, Factor Analysis, Anova and Chi-square test.

Review of Literature

Shanthini, G., & Radjaramane, V. (2018) The objective of the study is accomplished with the help of secondary data considered for a period of 15 years from 2000-01 to 2015-16. From

study it is observed that the growth rates of area, production and yield of coconut in India over the period were positive and significant except Kerala. The yield effect was the most important factor for an increase in production of coconut for all the states.

Ashik, A. (2018) The objective of study is to find out the socio-economic conditions of coir industry in Kerala. Result indicated that the problems faced by the coir industry are unavailability of labour, lack of government support towards traditional methods and labours face the problems of low wage rate, health issues

Fausayana, I., Abdullah, W. G., & Dawid, L. O. (2018) The aim of this study was to analysis the risks of coconut products marketing in Kendari City. Result reveals that the risk on coconut products marketing was mapped at low risk. High risk was more prevalent in the stage of processing. While medium risk was more prevalent in the stage of storing.

Hakimi, M., Shafiai, M., & Moi, M. R. (2017). This paper attempts to look at the possibility of collaboration of Islamic agricultural finance in agricultural land development realizing the farmers. It was found that the farmers at the survey areas faced the financial problems during the second cycle cultivating yet the farmers have the capability in saving at the financial institutions

Naik, J. N., & Nagaraja, G. (2017) examine the awareness and problems of respondents about the coconut marketing. The study has brought out the profitability involved in the cultivation and economic aspects of coconut. The present study has brought out the profitability involved in the cultivation and economic aspects of coconut.

Herman, M. (2016). This study was aimed at assessing the value chain analysis of the coconut subsector in Kenya. The study used descriptive cross sectional survey design and its population was comprised of forty two (42) SMEs engaged in coconut value addition. The findings of the study revealed that value addition in the coconut subsector is very important in Kenya and that various institutions play critical role in the value chain process.

Sathya (2015). To study the respondents perception and the level of satisfaction and examine the awareness of respondents about the coconut market. The present study has brought out the profitability involved in the cultivation and economic aspects of coconut.

Ayoob C. P. & Mohammed Usman & Suresh A., (2012) To examine the attitude of coconut growers towards the marketing co-operatives in Kerala. Findings of the study revealed that the attitude of growers towards the co-operative societies among the affiliations is significantly different. The attitude index showed that nine out of fourteen variables have not reached up to the level of positive attitude expected by the respondents.

Analysis and Discussion

This Chapter is so designed to analyse the demographic profile of the marketers who are involved in the marketing activities of coconut products. The Demographic information includes, gender of the respondents, residential nature, status of the family members, Business related information viz, Nature of Business, Business status, item of products, place of purchase, mode of payment, type of coconut sold, strategy adopted when products are not sold on time, shift system operated, practice of wage system, salary paid, remuneration paid, forms of remuneration, credit sales, information on bad debts, profit-earned in a year, mode of adjusting the loss, lack of awareness, opinion on infrastructural facilities, opinion on funds, problems in co-ordination, were included.

Table 1: Gender of the Respondent

S. No	Gender of the Respondent	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Male	140	70.0
2	Female	60	30.0
	Total	200	100

■ Male ■ Female

It is inferred from the table 1 that 140 (70%) of the respondents are male and 60 (30%) are female. It is concluded that majority 70% of the respondents are male.

Table 2: Residential House of the Respondent

S. No	Nature of Residence	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Own house	73	36.5
2	Rented Building	67	33.5
3	Leased house	60	30.0
	Total	200	100

From the above table 2 it is inferred that 73 (36.5%) of the respondents are living in their own house, 67 (33.5%) of the respondents are living in rented building and 60 (30%) of the respondents are living in leased house.

Table 3: Nature of unit

S. No	Nature of unit	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Cottage industry	26	13.0
2	Tiny unit	48	24.0
3	Small scale unit	34	17.0
4	SIDCO unit	41	20.5
5	Company	51	25.5
	Total	200	100

Table 3 describes the nature of unit. It is clear that 51 (25.5%) of the respondents' nature of unit was company, 48 (24%) of the respondents' nature of unit was tiny unit, followed with 41 (20.5%) of the respondents' nature of unit were SIDCO unit.

Table 4: Items produced

S.No	Items produced	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Coconut based products	43	21.5
2	Coconut wood based products	58	29.0
3	Coconut leaf based products	51	25.5
4	Coconut coir based products	48	24.0
	Total	200	100

The table 4.5 reveals that, 58 (29%) of the respondents were involved in the manufacturing of coconut wood based products, 51 (25.5%) of the respondents were involved in coconut leaf based products, 48 (24%) of the respondents were involved in coconut coir based products and 43 (21.5%) of the respondents were involved in coconut based products.

Table 5: Place of purchase of raw material

S. No	Place of purchase of raw material	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	From own coconut grove	44	22.0
2	From neighbour coconut grove	51	25.5
3	From open market	52	26.0
4	From co-operative societies	53	26.5
	Total	200	100

The table 5 reveals that, 53 (26.5%) of the respondents purchase their required raw materials from cooperative societies, 52 (26%) of the respondents purchase their required raw materials from open market, 51 (25.5%) of the purchase their required raw materials from neighbour coconut grove and 44 (22%) of the respondents purchase their required raw materials from their own coconut grove.

Table 6: Mode of sale

S.No	Mode of sale	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Cash sales	75	37.5
2	Credit sales	48	24.0
3	Both	77	38.5
	Total	200	100

A pie chart illustrating the distribution of sales modes. The chart is divided into three segments: a blue segment for 'Cash sales' representing 37.5%, an orange segment for 'Credit sales' representing 24%, and a grey segment for 'Both' representing 38.5%. A legend below the chart identifies the colors: blue for Cash sales, orange for Credit sales, and grey for Both.

Table 6 shows that, 77(38.5%) of the respondents sell their products for both credit as well as cash, 75 (37.5%) of the respondents sells their products for cash and 48 (24%) of the respondents sells their products for credit.

Table 7: Association between the nature of unit and the production problems faced. (Chi square).

H₀: There is no association between the nature of unit and the production problems faced.

S.No	Chi-square Test	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Result
1	Gender	6.818 ^a	4	0.146	NS
2	Items of coconut produced	9.999 ^a	12	0.616	NS
3	Items of raw materials required	15.324 ^a	16	0.501	NS
4	Place of purchase of raw material	13.020 ^a	12	0.368	NS
5	Mode of purchase	6.079 ^a	8	0.638	NS
6	Mode of payment when purchase on credit	0.970 ^a	8	0.914	NS
7	Type of coconut sold	12.957 ^a	12	0.372	NS
8	Strategy adopted when products are not sold in stipulated time	8.722 ^a	12	0.727	NS
9	Percentage of profit	6.556 ^a	8	0.585	NS
10	Infrastructural facilities	3.085 ^a	4	0.544	NS
11	Available infrastructural facilities	8.517 ^a	8	0.385	NS
12	Subsidy service	1.120 ^a	4	0.891	NS
13	Sources of subsidy service	13.960 ^a	12	0.303	NS
14	Sources of appointing workers	9.923 ^a	12	0.623	NS
15	Shift system	1.121 ^a	4	0.891	NS

16	Hours worked per shift	3.607 ^a	4	0.462	NS
17	Adoption of Minimum wages act	12.741	4	0.013	S

S – Significant, NS – Not Significant

It is found from the table 7, that the hypothesis is rejected (significant) in 1 cases and accepted (Not significant) in 16 cases. Hence it is concluded that nature of unit has impact on minimum wages act. Gender, items of coconut producing, raw material required, place of purchase required raw material, mode of purchase, mode of payment, type of coconut product selling, eatable coconut products are not in stipulated time, percentage of profits, infrastructural facilities, available infrastructural facilities, subsidies services, sources of subsidy loan, sources of appointing workers, shift system, hours per shift has no impact on nature of unit.

PRODUCTION PROBLEM – AN ANALYSIS

Table 8: KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.703
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	3787.707
	Df	120
	Sig.	.000

Table 4.50: Communalities		
	Initial	Extraction
Aging trees	1.000	.913
Water scarcity	1.000	.932
High cost of maintenance	1.000	.857
High cost of plants	1.000	.941
Non - availabilities of high yielding plants	1.000	.828
Non - availabilities of disease resistant planting material	1.000	.680
Lack of training regarding the selection of high yielding	1.000	.863
Attack of pests, fungal and bacterial diseases	1.000	.929
High cost of fertilizers	1.000	.918
High cost of electricity	1.000	.947
Lack of technical advice and expertise	1.000	.817
High rate of contamination	1.000	.711
Lack of disease resistant	1.000	.784
Handling problems	1.000	.806
Capital intensive nature	1.000	.802
Lack of attractive indigenous technology	1.000	.926
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

The above table Bartlett's test of sphericity and KAISER MEYER OLKIN measures of sample adequacy were used to test the appropriateness of the factor model. Bartlett's test was used to test the null hypothesis that the variables of this study are not correlated. Since the approximate chi square value is 3787.707 which is significant at 5% level, the test leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

The value of KMO statistics (0.703) was also large and it revealed that factor analysis might be considered as an appropriate technique for analysing the correlation matrix. The communality table showed the initial and extraction values.

ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE (ANOVA)

The clusters of various marketing problems faced by the producers has been analysed with production details, human resource information, financial assistance and customer relation through Analysis of Variance in order to find the significant difference.

H₀: There is no significant difference among various marketing problems faced by the producers and gender.

H₁: There is significant difference among various marketing problems faced by the producers and gender.

Source of Variance		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Lack of advice on technology and capital	Between Groups	.633	1	.633	1.192	.276	NS
	Within Groups	105.170	198	.531			
	Total	105.803	199				
Price hike on water plants and raw materials	Between Groups	.003	1	.003	.004	.950	NS
	Within Groups	133.053	198	.672			
	Total	133.056	199				
Absence of control over diseases	Between Groups	1.537	1	1.537	2.486	.116	NS
	Within Groups	122.392	198	.618			
	Total	123.928	199				
Lack of knowledge on hybrid tree cultivation	Between Groups	.069	1	.069	.140	.709	NS
	Within Groups	97.326	198	.492			
	Total	97.395	199				

The above table 9 ,indicates that various marketing problems faced by the producers do not have significant differences across gender. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected with respect to various marketing problems faced by the producers. The alternative hypothesis (H1) is accepted for other marketing problems.

H0: There is no significant difference among various marketing problems faced by the producers and nature of unit.

H1: There is significant difference among various marketing problems faced by the producers and nature of unit.

Table 10 : Significant difference among various marketing problems faced by the producers and nature of unit.(ANOVA)							
Source of Variance		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Lack of advice on technology and capital	Between Groups	2.312	4	.578	1.089	.363	NS
	Within Groups	103.491	195	.531			
	Total	105.803	199				
Price hike on water plants and raw materials	Between Groups	7.325	4	1.831	2.840	.025	S
	Within Groups	125.730	195	.645			
	Total	133.056	199				
Absence of control over diseases	Between Groups	1.609	4	.402	.641	.634	NS
	Within Groups	122.319	195	.627			
	Total	123.928	199				
Lack of knowledge on hybrid tree cultivation	Between Groups	1.381	4	.345	.701	.592	NS
	Within Groups	96.014	195	.492			
	Total	97.395	199				

The above table 10, indicates that various marketing problems faced by the producers do not have significant differences across nature of unit. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected with respect to various marketing problems faced by the producers. The alternative hypothesis (H1) is accepted for other marketing problems and the alternate hypothesis is rejected for Price hike on water plants and raw materials factor.

Findings

- Out of 200 respondents, 140 respondents are male and rest are female. Female respondents are few in number as compared to male and a 36.5 percent of the respondents are living in their own house.
- A 43.5 percent of the respondent's family members were studying and a 25.5 percent of the respondents had company as their nature of unit.
- A 29 percent of the respondents were selling coconut wood based products and a 26 percent of the respondents require coconut wood as raw material.
- A majority 26.5 percent of the respondent's purchase raw materials from cooperative societies and the mode of purchase was through both cash as well as credit accounting to 40. percent
- A 69.64 percent of the respondents make single payment when goods purchased on credit and a 21 percent of the respondents are selling eatable coconut products.
- A 50 percent of the respondents were selling eatable coconuts based on demand and a 35 percent of the respondents were not getting sufficient profit.
- A 72 percent of the respondents have infrastructural facilities and a 70 percent of the respondents are getting subsidy services and a 25.5 percent of the respondents are getting subsidies from coconut board.
- A 32 percent of the respondent appointed their own family members in business, and a 63 percent of the respondents adopt shift system.
- A 62.7 percent of the respondents work for 8 hours in a shift system and most of the respondents follow minimum wages act.
- A 61.5 percent of the respondents do not pay other than salary and a 50.6 percent of the respondent are paying bonus to their workers.
- A 55.6 percent of the respondent provides food to their workers as non – monetary benefits and a 56.5percent of the respondent does not follow piece rate system.
- A 56.5 percent of the respondent does not pay any bonus to the workers for producing more than the standard output.
- A majority 39.5 percent of the respondent pay only actual piece rate and a 41.5 percent of the respondent require skilled workers.
- A 36.1percent of the respondent require trained person as their skilled workers.

- A 41.5 percent of the respondents get training from their elders for coconut production.
- A majority 74.5 percent of the respondents avail facility from free training centre.
- A majority 42.3 percent of the respondent's get free training from coconut board.
- A 33 percent of the respondent learnt modern techniques from the special trainer's board.
- A 66.5 percent of the respondents have not received salary during training period.
- A 28.4 percent of the respondents have received half salary during the training period and a 31.5 percent of the respondents have learnt production of new products through special orders.

Conclusion

Agriculture is the main occupation of many in Coimbatore district, It has given an opportunity for the agriculturists to lead their life in a self-contempt way. Over the years the producers have faced different environments which made them survived in high latitudes, drought, soil, resistance and so on, of all these problems, the coconut industry has grown significantly by producing, marketing with the available infrastructure facilities. The farmers have to diverse their farming practices. This will give the additional revenue and ways for sustaining profit. The researchers, scientists, farmers have to be in a forum to exchange ideas and transmit the ideas in to action for enhancing sustainability.

Coconut marketing will bring addition revenue, if the market segmentations are properly made by concentrating the expectation of different customers groups. As the products of coconuts are lined up, different marketing strategies have to be adopted for better sales. The aspects of branding, customised marketing and reorienting towards value addition will fetch better results.

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